

Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part XI.
Variation of Optical Refractivity during the
Coagulation of Colloid Manganese Dioxide
and new Evidence for the Discontinuity
of the Change.

BY SHRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI AND S. JAYA RAO.

Previous studies in these series (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 329; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 599; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 133; Joshi and Iyengar, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 555, 573; Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 797; also *J. chim. Phys.*, 1935, **32**, 455-459; *Proc. Acad. Sci., U. P.*, 1935, **5**, 41-45) have largely dealt with the results of viscosity measurements during the coagulation of a number of sols by various electrolytes, especially in the *slow* region. One outstanding result of these investigations has been to demonstrate that failure to recognise the possible discontinuity in time of the progress of a coagulation especially in the *slow* region constitutes the chief deficiency in the current theories of the kinetics of the change as developed by Smoluchowski (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, **92**, 129), Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, pp. 442-450) and others. In order to obtain more information about the factors responsible for the break down of these theories, it was thought instructive to examine the change by use of a method for measuring coagulation, different from the ones employed previously (*loc. cit.*; *cf.* also, Joshi and Prabhu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 11, 337; Joshi and Phansalkar, *ibid.*, 1932, **9**, 157; Joshi and Lal, *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 61). A reference to the literature of the subject showed that a change in the refractive index does not appear to have been used as a measure of the corresponding degree of coagulation. From the very beginning of work in this line (*cf.* Joshi and Godbole, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Congress*, 1931, p. 135; especially, *cf.* Joshi and Jaya Rao, *ibid.*, 1934, p. 210; also, Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, p. 213) was realised the marked convenience and sensitivity of this method. Of this, the experiments on

colloid manganese dioxide (*cf.* also Joshi and Lal, *loc. cit.*) now to be described, would appear to be the first detailed application in the field of coagulation kinetics.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sol was prepared by adding slowly concentrated ammonia, a few drops at a time, to a boiling solution of potassium permanganate. The excess of ammonia was boiled off after failing to note any traces of the permanganate in a given sample of the sol after coagulation with barium chloride. The sol thus prepared contained potassium hydroxide in small amounts which is produced in the interaction between ammonia and permanganate (Cuy, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 415; *cf.* also Joshi and Narayan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 883); with this residual amount of alkali, the stability of the colloid was found to be very satisfactory. The colloid was stocked in silica vessels. Its content was estimated by the addition of a known volume of standard oxalic acid acidified with sulphuric acid, and the titration of the excess with standard permanganate. The colloid content was kept constant at 2.06 g. MnO_2 per litre in the coagulating mixture in all these experiments.

The refractive index was determined for the sodium light with a Pulfrich refractometer capable of giving results correct to the fifth decimal place. One c.c. of the colloid preheated to 30° was introduced into the cell of the refractometer which was brought previously to the above temperature. The concentration of the coagulator was adjusted by preliminary experiments so that a measurable change in the refractive index was produced during about 2-3 hours at least. An equal amount of the electrolyte solution preheated as above was then carefully added to the colloid and the mixture stirred twice. Measurement of the refractive index was then started; it was discontinued when (i) the mixture showed a constant refractivity over an appreciably long period, (ii) or, the coagulating mixture became too opaque to let any light through, (iii) or, the coagulation had advanced so far as to produce optical heterogeneities due to particles of the coagulum in the cell of the refractometer. In view of the fact that but small percentage changes in the refractive index were produced during any of the coagulations studied in these experiments, the susceptibility of this quantity to temperature variations, and also the sensitivity of the instrument used, control of the temperature was found to be an important factor in order to yield

accurate and reproducible results. This was kept constant at 30° , the utmost fluctuations being within $1/20^\circ$ to $1/10^\circ$, except during experiments referred to in curve 1 in Fig. 6 showing the influence of the temperature on the refractive index of the colloid. This constancy of temperature was more than that required for the purpose of this work (*vide infra*). These results are shown by refractive index—time curves in Figs. 1-5. In order to facilitate comparison, the same scale, (*viz.* one unit on the abscissa = 10 minutes, and one on the ordinate = 0.00050 change in μ , the refractive index, except in curves 1, 2 in

FIG. 1.

Fig. 4) has been employed in all the figures. The origin for any one of a family of curves has shifted along the ordinate to prevent neighbouring curves from coalescing. This also served appreciably to economise space in the figures. Curves in Fig. 1 give μ -time curves when the coagulator concentration was varied in the range 2.5 to 50 m. mols of potassium chloride in the coagulating mixture. This and the next, Fig. 2, show data for the so-called lyotropic series (HCl, Li_2SO_4 , NaCl, KCl and NH_4Cl). Results with strontium chloride and lanthanum nitrate are shown in Fig. 3. Aluminium chloride (*cf.* Fig. 4) behaved differently from lanthanum nitrate although both are trivalent. Only a few typical results with a tetravalent coagulator, *e.g.*, thorium nitrate are shown in Fig. 5. Experiments were also made with different concentrations of cerium nitrate. These curves were found to be essentially similar to those due to thorium nitrate, and so have not been shown. For the same reason, curves with a number of barium chloride (*cf.* Fig. 3) concentrations, as also those corresponding to varying colloid contents and different amounts of potassium chloride used as a coagulant (*cf.* Fig. 1) have been deleted. Curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 6 show respectively the influence of temperature and of the colloid content on the refractive index of the sol used in this work.

DISCUSSIONS.

The information available in the literature in regard to the optical refractivity of the colloid state during its characteristic changes is markedly insufficient in respect of data and theory. Walpole (*Kolloid Z.*, 1913, 13, 241), who was perhaps the first to work in this line, studied the influence on the refractive index of aqueous gelatine of (i) the addition of the chloride, sulphate and thiocyanate of ammonia, of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide, (ii) changing the temperature and the concentration, and (iii) transition from the sol to the gel condition. He found that the changes in μ , the refractive index were related linearly to the corresponding densities. Wintgen (*ibid.*, 1921, 28, 5) confirmed this from observations with colloid arsenious and antimony sulphides, silicic and molybdic acids, ferric hydroxide and tannin. The recent accurate work of Boutaric and co-workers (*Compt. rend.*, 1927, 185, 892; *Rev. gen. Colloid*, 1927, 5, 658) using an interference refractometer has shown that the difference between the refractive index of the sol and that for the medium is propor-

tional to the colloid content. Data on colloid manganese dioxide shown by curve 2, Fig. 6 show that μ varies linearly with respect to colloid content as observed by the above workers. At very low proportions of the dispersed phase, however, it is seen that μ rises almost insensibly by increasing the colloid content of the sol. Similar results (to be published shortly) were obtained by Mr. G. R. Godbole in these laboratories in the case of colloid arsenious sulphide. Curve 1 in Fig. 6 show that μ diminishes linearly by increasing the temperature;

FIG. 2.

1'33257

FIG. 3.

1'33262

the curve shows a break at about 33° . This would appear to be associated partly with some change in the constitution of the dispersion medium, *viz.*, water, since a similar discontinuity has been observed by Osborn (*Phys. Rev.*, 1912, 35, 216) in the μ -temperature curve for pure water.

Curves of Figs. 1—5 show that variations in μ , attendant on the various types of coagulations, are quite appreciable and irregular. The latter feature is found to be marked especially in the case of univalent coagulations. A number of experiments was made to see if this apparent irregularity was due to any experimental error. At high concentrations, that is, in moderately rapid coagulations, the results were both more uniform and satisfactorily reproducible. In very slow coagulations the reproducibility was found to be less. This, however, could not be traced to any deficiency in the accuracy and the sensitivity of apparatus. Moreover, this was observed generally towards the final stages of the coagulation. Some of the results obtained in this connection are interesting. Comparing for example curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 1 due to the least and the largest concentration of the electrolyte, it is seen that the former shows more fluctuations. It was possible to reproduce all points in curve 2 in Fig. 1 corresponding to rapid coagulation. When the experiment corresponding to curve 1 shown by triangles was repeated a number of times, in the majority of cases all the points shown on the curve 1, Fig. 1 were obtained; the two points which were sometimes missed were at α and β , in the minimum; they, however, appeared during the coagulation at positions shown by the dotted triangles. A similar effect was observed in curve 3, Fig. 1 shown by continuous squares corresponding to 25 millimols of KCl; points γ and δ appeared at positions shown by corresponding dotted squares in some of the repetitions of the experiments. Similar results were obtained in the reproductions of other results which have not been shown for want of space, and whose common indication was that points generally towards the close of the coagulation did not appear at the same time, and then, a whole fluctuation was missed, so that the final section showing a constancy of refractive index appeared earlier. On comparing these curves in Fig. 1 for the slowest coagulations with curves in Figs. 2—5, it is seen that the former do not show an *overall* change in the refractive index consequent upon coagulation. Precisely similar results were obtained earlier (Joshi and Viswanath, *loc. cit.*) where it was found that while moderately rapid coagulations of colloid arsenious sulphide yielded

uniform and progressively rising viscosity-time curves, *slow* coagulations corresponded markedly to discontinuous changes without a *net* rise of viscosity produced during the period observed. This has been confirmed by subsequent results in the case of numerous other coagulations (Joshi and coworkers, *loc. cit.*).

FIG. 4.

In view of the sensitivity of μ to temperature changes, it is important to see that these latter are not responsible for the observed fluctuations on the μ —time curves. From the data obtained for the influence of temperature on μ (*cf.* Fig. 6), it is seen for example that the discontinuities on the various μ —time curves in Fig. 1 correspond to temperature changes in the range $1-6^\circ$. This is definitely inadmissible, since the temperature of the coagulating system was certainly constant within 0.1 to 0.05° . The possibility of the accumulation of coagulum on the face of the prism in the refractometer was also examined. In the first instance, the mixture was well stirred throughout the progress of the coagulation and secondly with a given colloid a deposition of its precipitate would alter μ in the same sense in all coagulations irrespective of the nature of the coagulant, which is contrary to facts as observed here. While results in Fig. 2, obtained with other monovalent coagulants, are substantially similar to those discussed already in the case of KCl in Fig. 1, it is interesting to see from Fig. 3 that the

influence of the trivalent lanthanum and bivalent strontium salts is to raise μ during coagulation. Results with barium chloride were clearly analogous.

The specificity of the influence of the coagulant on μ change is further brought out by curves in Figs. 4 and 5, where in coagulations

FIG. 5.

by thorium nitrate and aluminium chloride, μ is seen to change in a sense opposite to that observed previously in Fig. 3. One rather suggestive and general result from curves in Figs. 1-5 is that the progress of coagulation as recorded by μ -change is markedly discontinuous, and that this feature is more pronounced the slower the coagulation, especially with univalent coagulants. The concentration of the coagulator would appear to determine both the number and duration of each of these zones of coagulation, during any one of which μ remains constant and changes abruptly to a new value which in its turn prevails for a time, and so on. In earlier papers in this series (*loc. cit.*) on the deficiency in the application of Smoluchowski's theory of the kinetics of coagulation (*loc. cit.*) the view was emphasized on experimental grounds that contrary to Smoluchowski's fundamental assumption, coagulation was more complex than a mere continued aggregation of primary particles, and also that the process was not time continuous, especially in the 'slow' region. The results in Figs. 1-5 support this view, and also serve to indicate the utility of refractive index measurements as a systematic and sensitive means of exploring the course of coagulation.

FIG. 6.

SUMMARY.

1. Progress of coagulations of colloid manganese dioxide by different concentrated solutions of HCl, Li_2SO_4 , NaCl, KCl, NH_4Cl , SrCl_2 , $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ has been followed by measurement of μ , the refractive index with a Pulfrich refractometer.

2. The nature of the μ -time curve depends upon the nature and the concentration of the coagulant.

3. These curves have been found to be discontinuous in all the cases examined. It is postulated that coagulation is not time continuous, but occurs through successive and discontinuous stages called "Zones of coagulation" which tend to become conspicuous in the *slow* region.

4. μ -and the colloid content, and μ -and temperature were found to be related linearly, except for very small concentrations of the sol and also at lower temperatures.

